

Popular Design and Cultural Identities – Emotional Exchange: Study Cases in Israel

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Abstract

This paper's premises are the interrelations between popular design and cultural identity acting through a strong emotional presence imbedded in popular design, toward satisfying the strong desire haunting the collective and the individual to psychologically and culturally identify through material and visual expressions. These premises are based on the seminal perspectives of a novel writer (Pamuk), a psychotherapist (Freud), a cultural critic-mythologue (Barthes) and notorious designers.

Based on these premises a twofold methodology is suggested for a better investigation of study cases: a semiotic analysis combined with examination of "relational existence" in other cultural expression such as, literature, popular songs, fine art, cinema, advertisements, cultural research, as well as conceptual design works. This methodology is implemented here on several study cases, all forming part of typical Israeli urban texture: the sun heated boilers on roofs, the lottery corporate identity, the cars stickers, the headlines on daily newspapers and the "oriental restaurant". The analysis is trying to show how these cases are associated with nostalgic and/or aggressive emotions through the impact of design characteristics and the filters of their "relational existence". Also it addresses such questions as, who are responsible for that impact. What kind of agenda and whose interests this emotional presence and impact serves?

The writer, the psychotherapist and the mythologue

Wandering through the city, searching two disappeared souls, Galip, the protagonist of Pamuk's **The Black Book** see in objects signs of secret message he can decipher as if they were human faces (Pamuk 1998: 235). Throughout the entire novel Galip is going through a painful Odyssey in deciphering the signs and expressions of his metropolis, in order to scrutinize his own personal and cultural identity. That kind of scrutiny can be associated with Freud dream decoding system (1900) consisting of attaching to objects in a dream an indirect meaning, by sorts of associations: semantic, visual or memorial. In parallel, Galip's deciphering labor reminds of Barthes (1957) system for unmasking myths based on semiology. Barthes deals with those contemporary myths that haunt our cultural existence and environments, pretending they are natural phenomena. The Bartheian approach to "collective representations" (an article, a photo, a car, an ad, a hair design in a movie, toys, plastic material, etc.) as a set of signs enable to demystify them and reveal their artificial, conventional and manipulative nature. Barthes, through his way of writing, insists on

combining the point of view of both, an objective mythologue researcher and a subjective writer [1].

Pamuk "writes into" his protagonists fears and identity, through the metropolis; Freud's system has targeted the individual's unconsciousness via his dreamed objects or environments, and Barthes' deciphering system serve scrutinizing culture through collective, mostly imposed desires and beliefs. Out of different motives though, all three address contemporary popular culture objects or environments as **signs**, for their powerful influence on individuals or societies, in shaping their dreams and identities through emotional impact.

The designers perspective

Examining these "collective representations", expressions of popular culture from the point of view of designers brings up yet another perspective on their meanings and emotional impact. Many designers have shown interest and studied popular objects and environments, stressing their morphological, functional and cultural aspects, mainly out of professional interest. Designers have addressed them, as "popular design", "pop icons" or "vernacular design". Popular design is a general term comprising the two others. "Pop icons", meaning popular persons, characters (Madonna), or objects (coca cola bottle) adored and admired by masses like religious sacred images. In recent years, the "web icons" are joining the reservoir of popular products that are accumulating anonymously in "real" physical environments. Is either of these icons also vernacular? The term "vernacular design", especially diffused by the designer Tibor Kalman, has been adopted from architecture theory. Vernacular architecture is understood both as a phenomenon and as a concept. It designates a locally rooted building or a built environment that grew out of local natural and cultural conditions to which they owe their specific features and not to an architect. Kalman had a huge collection of found objects exhibited in the famous exhibition **Tiborcity**: hair pine, buttons, chip packages, ad fliers, bus tickets, envelopes, etc. He declared love to these objects for their simplicity, ugliness and anonymity (Farrelly, 1998: 12). From Modernists designers like Charles and Ray Eames [2], to Radicals like the Italian "anti-designers" groups (Alchemia, Superstudio, Archizoom etc.) (Branzi 1984) and the "undesigners" such as Tibor Kalman and his followers (Poynor 2002), to designers with sustainable conviction (Watkins 1994), all have been collecting those popular iconic and /or vernacular design items. They have been studying it, admiring it, conceptualizing it, being nostalgic about it or attaching to it a specific cultural identity they

are committed to preserve in their design, thus adopting from architecture the idea of vernacular as a professional concept. Designers acting as anthropologists and "culturally responsible" exist in Israel as well. They collect and conceptualize such local "popular collective representations" thus recognizing them as part of local/Israeli cultural patrimony or heritage (Tarazi 2001). For example, the senior designer David Tartakover has a collection of "Israeliana", of Zionist heritage such as, posters, greeting cards, objects, popular books, photographs. Tartakover designed and exhibited collages and posters based on his collected items. He has also co-written an illustrated lexicon of terms related to everyday life in Israel during the fifties and sixties from Jewish Israeli perspective, including visuals from this époque (Tartakover and Dankner 1996). One of the main reasons for publishing this Lexicon, as stated in the introduction, was nostalgia.

The interest of designers on popular design has developed throughout the 20th century from a formalistic (based on high Modernistic ideas) into cultural interests (based on Postmodern thought) of anthropological and/or ideological nature. The latter express the idea about design practice, being involved with understanding, using and respecting what they recognize as iconic or/end vernacular design. Some of them are being quite emotional about it.

Popular design and cultural identity by emotional tie

The, subjective, scientific or professional perspectives of the writer, the psychotherapist, the cultural critic or mythologue and the designer, seem to suggest interrelations between popular design and cultural identity. Popular design generates a sense of identity within a culture (national, ethnic or other social group) or within an individual (a common person, a novel protagonist or a designer). Whereas, cultural identity is the dominant factor that generates the climate for popular design products or environments. It also seems that this symbiotic relation is working through a strong emotional presence imbedded in popular design. This emotional presence acts toward satisfying the strong desire that haunt the collective as well as the individual to psychologically and culturally identify through material and visual expressions. This last suggestion can be based not only on the above mentioned ways of understanding the cultural and psychological role of popular design, but also on anthropological research conducted on consumption (Douglas and Isherwood 1979). John Walker (1989:128) has presented it clearly: goods are desired also because they represent "a way of imposing identity and sense on the environment". Therefore, this emotional presence detected, on a

general level, as strongly associated with popular design acting upon cultural identity, can be, in a case analysis confirmed by or revealed through the sensitive filters of observations and interpretations focused on them by writers, artists, researchers and designers.

This emotional presence generated by and attached to popular design, either in dream, in memory or in reality is under influence of several factors affecting different aspects of their existence. These every day objects and environments are designed by anonymous designers and used and experienced by anonymous masses. Some of them which grew for ages as archetypal or/and local items, are considered as "natural and immortal" part of culture (Forty 1992). Some of them are attached to a specific period, kept in museums glass cases (subject to formal or cultural research) or in collections, were they will acquire the status of admired and longed objects. They can show up again in fashion revivals, commercially created by, marketing and designers (vintage design). Some of them are adored and missed items or environments, considered as pop icons by critics and thus catalogued, idolized and immortalized by them and by the masses, or/and by artists, writers, designers. Most of them are still part of everyday life and remain unnoticed, but their emotional presence and impact is revealed in another popular expression, like popular songs, cinema, and design, or in poetry, literature, or a work of art.

A twofold methodology

Contending that emotional presence of popular design is the main power standing behind its conversation with cultural identities, I suggest a twofold methodology of two lenses to better investigate popular design within a culture or a society. The first is directed towards the very existence of the case investigated within its context, as a semiotic **sign**. The second is directed towards the case "relational existence", digested or appropriated by another cultural expression, such as, poetry, literature, popular songs, social phenomena, fine art, cinema, advertisements, cultural research, publicist writing, as well as conceptual design works. This double cross examination holds the potential to provide a larger scope of insight into the investigated case. Moreover, the reflective relation directed towards it can reveal or sharpen its actual emotional presence in its association to cultural identity, which might remain unnoticed or hidden in its own existence as a **sign**. The key question, posed as a work hypothesis should be about the nature and circumstances of its emotional or mythological presence and cultural identity it generates. Other questions stem from it: what makes the

objects or environments generate this emotional presence, emotional impact or myths? Who are responsible for that impact? What kind of agenda and whose interests this emotional presence serves?

The study cases

The sun heated boilers on the roofs, the national lottery corporate identity, the slogans stickers on cars, the headlines on daily newspapers and the so called "oriental restaurants" are the local Israeli study cases I have chosen to investigate on the basis of the above presented premises and methodology. The choice of these cases is based on common features which define "semiotically" their scope of existence. They all form an integral part of urban texture and are present in every city in Israel. They can be defined in themselves as complex signs that are connected integrally to a more complex set of signs within the urban texture. Their complexity resides in being inseparable from another object or by being recognized as a whole body comprising different objects. As complex signs they exist in gradual integrality within the urban context. Thus the sun heated boilers are not to disconnect from the buildings they stand on and these buildings are part of the city dwellings and part of the city skyline; the slogan stickers are integral part of cars which are dynamic part of the city roads in movement or parked; the headlines are integral part of newspapers, presented on stands on sidewalks in front of kiosks; the national lottery corporate identity, which is particularly complex, is comprised of many parts besides its logotype: the booths, the ads, the tickets; much the same, the "oriental restaurant" comprises many characteristic parts, such as the open façade to the street, the stainless-steel ware, the large mirror, the clear tiles covering the wall, etc. In spite of their complexity and their being part of a staggered system of **signs**, all these cases are known by any city visitor or dweller as unities for their own sakes and can be recognized as **signifiers** - some of the most characteristic traits of the urban face in Israel.

The Sun-Heated boiler

The **signifier** is a structure assembled of a big white or grey metal water cylindrical container with black flat receptacles posed in an angle at the container's feet - standing upright on a roof of an apartment building, usually as part of a series, visible at distances The **signified** is the concept of saving electricity by using solar energy for heating water per private, family size needs. The **sign** is an economical solar water heater device for private use, imposingly visible in groups on apartment building roofs. The referent is the visible operation of heating

water by the sun, visibility enabled by the prominent bare and rude functional structure. The sun heated boilers have been introduced as a local patent in the beginning of the sixties and they started to be installed privately on roofs of relatively new apartment buildings of middle-class neighborhoods everywhere. Since the end of the eighties, the water containers are hidden inside the structure of new apartment buildings, where the black flat receptacles became part of post-modernist roofs design. Today, the sun heated boilers are associated almost exclusively with old neglected modernists building apartments of low-middle class neighborhoods, diffused along roads in every city. The naked rudeness of their design transmits a presence of aggressiveness combined with the poor condition of the apartment building they crown. Together they bear witness to an identity of a social class (low middle) whose deteriorated dwelling condition is attached to the period of the first 30 years of Israel existence as a state. Several art works, films and popular songs focus on the sun heated boilers [3]. They relate emotionally to it, sometimes with other urban neglected features (television antennas, falling plaster, or broken window), as a metaphor for rudeness, aggressiveness combined with nostalgic sadness addressing the time lost and social deterioration.

Figure 1, Sun Heated boilers on roofs: typical urban skyline of Israeli towns

slogan stickers on cars

The **signifier** is plastic strips printed with different slogans (political, religious, philosophical, military, about careful driving) stacked on private cars or on other vehicles mostly on the rear

window and sometimes on the bumper. The **signified** is the concept of self expression of cars owners (or drivers) through slogans they identify with, by diffusing them among other drivers and passing by. The **sign** is a medium of alternative communication diffusing slogans drivers are willing to identify with. In Israel this phenomenon has developed only in the last 15 years and according to a comparative research that was conducted in 1996 it probably has substituted the slogan graffiti spread out in the eighties and became a central alternative communication medium. (Olinsky 1996). Most of the designers are anonymous professionals working for the organizations, especially during political campaigns. The first sticker though was designed by the designer David Tartakover for the "Peace Now" movement in the beginning of the eighties. Most of the messages on the cars in Israel are political (compared to minor percentage in the US). The stickers are mostly distributed free of charge to the drivers by political, religious, civil or other organizations of interest. Other signifying features are the sharpness of the messages and the designs: sharp contrasting colors (red, blue, green, black) and very limited typographic design. Actually, certain types like certain colors are used for certain messages (blue for patriotic messages, red and black for menacing ones); certain typography is associated with specific words in certain messages (the word peace in the "peace now" seminal slogan), but is used for different word in contra messages. These design features are meant to enhance the directness and aggressiveness of the messages which are mostly political. One can deduce that the Israeli public or at least the middle upper class car owners are very involved politically. In fact, sticking a free, already designed slogan on one's car dose not requires much involvement or investment. The interest behind it reveals a desire of belonging to a group, (other car owners) which one can identify easily with its conviction. The slogan car sticker is addressed by various "filters". In the academia, through sociological research, in a designers exhibition named "sticker, the media of the country"[4]. No less interesting is the phenomenon of addressing the stickers on the web, were they are being documented; new ones are created by users in relations to the car stickers. Through the web. Car stickers are also intensively collected, where they have become already memorabilia items. From dynamic sharp and aggressive slogans on cars, expressing the range of Israeli convictions throughout the cities and roads they turned into nostalgic memory lane joining the rest of "Israeliana".

Figure 2, Slogan stickers on a car: combination of messages - politics, military and sport.

The headlines on daily newspapers

The **signifier** is the huge sensational titles with thick typography and colored background, spread out on the first page of the daily newspapers displayed for sale on stands in front of kiosks. The **signified** is the concept of effectively spreading news and selling them through sensational blunt design and content. The **sign** is the headlines as bluntly designed and emotionally formulated on the newspaper displayed for sale, attract the attention of the passing by inciting them to stop and read the headlines and thus "sell" them distorted information. The referent of this sign is the very diffusion of the kind of messages jumping far ahead out of the displayed newspaper. This phenomenon of devoting the first page mainly to headlines thus bluntly designed and put combined only with color photographs and subtitles, relegating the actual reportage connected to these headlines to the inner pages, has developed through the nineties and has been rooted in the two main daily newspapers ("Maariv" and "Yedioth Aharonot"). The media critic, Daniel Dor (2001) has demonstrated how very often exist a too big gap in content between the reportage and the headlines which operate through their design and content almost as slogans and not as information as it should be. Passing by the kiosks do not have to buy the paper or read the inner pages. They are unwillingly trapped by the emotional impact of the one-sided bluntly put and designed headlines they can not avoid grasping by. These headlines are mostly frightening, menacing

and worrying, but in the same time, because they are "shouting" on a daily basis they give the general public a sense of belonging, of being part of a community having the same fate, same opinion on the events, saving them the efforts to read farther and make judgments. That is well reflected in the slogans advertising the two newspapers: "Maariv, newspaper for all" and "Yediot Aharonot, the Newspaper of the country". The newspaper in general and the front page headlines in particular have been many times addressed in works of art (Gilerman 2002). They mostly relate to them in a critical way, using the emotional blunt design into different, usually ironic, directions. The artist Belo Semion Finaro, for example created a rug designed as a front page newspaper [5].

Figure 3, Daily newspapers on stands in-front of a kiosk, general view.

Figure 4, Headlines of daily newspapers pile and a view on a front page.

The Lottery corporate identity

The **signifier** is all contained in a small booth for selling a variety of lottery tickets issued by the national corporation ("Mifal Hapais"). Incorporated in it are ads in form of posters and signage. It stands in every corner on both sides of the street, easily recognized from far distance by its centralized trapezoidal undefined shapes and its orange and blue colors ornate

with sparkling stares that are also part of the logotype. The **signified** is the concept of exploiting human desire, or hope, to win in a lottery and become a millionaire. The **sign** is the complex and visually aggressive and dominant apparatus for inserting hope/illusion in people's minds, directed to sell lottery tickets to maximum persons. The referent is the big lottery itself that takes place twice a week and is presented on television as a big show, beside the scratching tickets where one can find out the result on the spot by the booth. In parallel to the selling and marketing machinery the "Mifal Hapais" corporation maintains a whole apparatus of public relation, advertising its funding activities for the community, distributing all kinds of presents to its subscribers, among them a booklet of "classic Israeli songs", and documenting its history in its website. In a special page called "Nostalgia", the visitor can study a collection of old posters from the beginning of the corporation in the fifties and a series of tickets issued especially for the 50th anniversary of Israel, with photographs of key events in Israeli history. In this case, there are no filtered views. The complex corporate apparatus is served bluntly by both aggressive and seductive design and marketing strategies. The design, contrasting colors, a fairy tale Disney style booths covered with candy-like stares, is combined with soft strategy, using nostalgia to stress national identity.

Figure 5, National lottery station in each corner of the street.

Figure 6, National lottery station: general view from the back and a detail of the front window.

The "oriental restaurant"

The **signifier** is an open to the street restaurant that sell middle-eastern food (known in Israel as "oriental food"), such as falafel, humus, shish-kebab, shawarma, kinds of salads and soft drinks. A take-away, on counter, or on plastic chair and table eating. It has characteristic items and design, such as a counter containing behind a glass the food in stainless-steel ware, a special folding stand designed for serving the stuffed pita bread. The back walls are covered

with clear blue or white tiles and a large mirror; all combined with the soft drinks refrigerator internationally branded. The **signified** is the concept of "oriental food" as defining an eclectic middle-eastern food. The **sign** is the "oriental restaurant" with its characteristic design, appropriating the regional disparate dishes and culture into a mythifying concept, by means of eclecticism and redesign into an aggressive metallic and yet shining slicked look. The referent is the non-chain operation of "oriental restaurants", throughout the country, yet distanced from the authentic local Palestinian restaurant. This phenomenon was documented by a group of Israeli designers who found out that such characteristics of the "oriental restaurant" can be detected as well in Palestinian restaurants within Israel and beyond the green line in the Palestinian territories. However, to my assessment, it does not generate the same cultural identity in Israeli cities as in Palestinian cities. In Israel, it seems to be an expression of appropriation that curiously serves as a focal point of social assimilation in the Israeli society. This has created a kind of all Israeli cultural identity that meets, in a sense, through anonymous popular design characteristics the Palestinian cultural identity which has yet to be investigated concerning this case. The group of designers has created a conceptual exhibition where they displayed designed and redesigned items based on the characteristics of the documented "oriental restaurant" [6]. The filter of the exhibition is a double one: the Israeli's and the designer's. They mostly turned the aggressive slicked appearance into an exclusive real expensive design stressing the appropriation and distancing from the authentic, but in the same time missing the popular cultural identity expressed by the aggressive presence imbedded into the concept of "oriental".

Figure 7, An "Oriental Restaurant": general view from the street and a closer view of the outer counter on stainless steel ware.

Figure 8, An "Oriental Restaurant": a view of the inner sitting counter and the large mirror.

Figure 9, "Oriental Restaurant", the exhibition at Ami Stienitz gallery in Tel Aviv, January 2000: general view.

Summary

The above presented study cases have aspects of vernacular design in the sense that most of their designers are professionals but remain anonymous. These cases grew out of popular "all Israeli" cultural climate and under social conditions of urban low middle class, on the background of an overall multicultural society torn by inner conflicts. Most of the cases have acquired the status of popular icons in the sense that they are being collected or being

admired in popular songs or conceptualize in exhibitions, reflected in self public relation, or in memory lane lexicon. All these case studies are associated with nostalgic sentiments and/or aggressive emotions. Aggressiveness is mostly generated by the design characteristics and the content of the messages. This is counterbalanced by emotional yearning to the objects and to periods of the near past associated with them. In some cases, these two opposed feelings seem to serve an agenda issued by some business corporations, political organization or newspapers editors and owners in order to unite the society around some kind of consensual national identity. What does it says about Israeli main stream society? About its urban life? About its aspirations? Is it the average city dweller willingly tolerates this emotional dichotomy or even aspires to it? Based on these study cases, no accurate answers can be presented. Better insights to the complexity of vernacular design as generating and revealing cultural identities through emotional presence can be achieved by a more comprehensive research. I suggest it as a comparative research conducted on a twofold methodology and on global and regional backgrounds.

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NOTES:

[1] The purpose of *Mythologies* was clearly indicated by Barthes in his introduction to the 1979 edition of *Mythologies* – a year before his death and 22 years after its first publication.

[2] See in *The Work of Charles & Ray Eames, a Legacy of invention* 1999: the exhibition was organized by the Library of Congress in partnership with the Vitra Design Museum. The on line exhibition: <http://www.loc.gov/exhibits/eames/>

[3] Doron Rabina, an installation in the exhibition "the Road to Lod" 2003, in Kalisher gallery in Tel Aviv; "Happiness without end", a film by Igeal Burshtein, 1996; Moshe Wasana, a video art in the exhibition "The Israeli object", 2002, Jerusalem; "In the Sad Side of the Road", a popular song by Iankale Rotblit: "The Sun-Heated Boiler and the Antena", a popular song by Ain Hillel.

[4] It took place in the "Ascola gallery for design" in 1998.

[5] Among the artists who addressed headlines and journalistic photograph are: Moti Misrahi, Sigalit Landau, Rafi Lavie and Belo Semion Fainaro.

[6] The exhibition "Oriental Restaurant" by Dov Gansheroa, Esri Tarazi, Zivia Sharon, Sefi Hefetz, in Ami Steinitz, Contemporary Art Gallery in January, 2000.

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